

INDIGENOUS METHODS OF CRIME CONTROL: A PANACEA FOR SOCIAL ORDER IN BEKWARRA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Dorn Ckclaimz Enamhe
Department of Social Works
University of Calabar
dornckclaimz@yahoo.com , 08098701005

Walter Omang Ogar
Department of Sociology
Federal University Birnin Kebbi
walter.ogar@fubk.edu.ng, 08134716334

Asuquo, Mfon Effiong
Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Akwa Ibom State University
mfonasuquo@aksu.edu.ng, 07035490011

Eno Nnamdie Ekpo
15 Aba Street, Offot Road, Abak L.G.A
enonamdie76@gmail.com, 07065330494, 0802786105

Elizabeth Njo Obimbua
Department of Sociology
Federal University, Gusau
elizabethobimbua@fugusau.edu.ng, 08069835183

Abstract

This study Examined Indigenous Methods of Crime Control in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. Crime is a social problem that has directly contributed to the economic set-back of many nations including Nigeria, which directly reduces the quality of life of individual and communities. It is a phenomenon that bedeviling the nation and the steps taken by government it seems to be inadequate as Crime continues to spread like fire in dry season. Existing studies on Crime and its control have focused on the use of modern methods which are at variance with culture of the various societies, while little attention is paid to Crime Control mechanisms of Indigenous Methods of Crime Control in Bekwarra nation. The inability of government to adequately tackle the menace of crime has led to fears among the people as security of lives and property is perpetually threatened. This has impacted negatively on the country that is striving to be among developed nations in the World. This study aims at as to x- ray the traditional methods of crime control in Bekwarra. The paper examined how Crime and criminal related activities were addressed in the past with a view that if these methods can be applied in recent time to arrest the rise in crime, this may reduce crime in present Nigeria since the modern or western methods have not dealt

with significantly. Methodology used in the paper was a qualitative research method (FGD, IDI and Ki). To explain the phenomenon of crime, Anomic theory was adopted. The findings showed that there is significant relationship between modern methods of crime control and Indigenous Methods of Crime Control. Despite the sophistication weapons used by the security agents has no significantly reduce or address the crime rate. The study recommended among others, the use of Indigenous Methods of Crime Control mechanisms with modern methods side by side to complement the efforts to fight crime in Nigeria in order to pave way for good governance and social order in the society.

Keywords: Indigenous, Crime Control, Methods, Panacea and Social Order

Introduction

The excess of this paper is to assess and appreciate the effectiveness of traditional methods of crime control in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State. One of the greatest problem has been to find plausible answers to the age-long question: “How is social order possible considering the nature of man as being wick, brutality, selfishness, and unreasonableness in his state of nature” Thomas Hobbes (1589-1670) in his greatest wisdom, “The Leviathan (Appredoria, 2003) provide an inspiring and motivating answer with his 'social contract' thesis as a plausible solution to this intellectual curiosity with regard to possibility of social order giving the wicked nature of man in his state of nature, as he informs us, “man is essentially selfish moved by his passion not by reason, living without any common power set over them,, it becomes a perpetual struggle of all against all, a situation of (anarchy)” (Appadoria, 2003:22). And to curb these excess of man in his state of nature, men must give up their natural rights to a constituted body (by way of social contract) that can help, with the authority conferred on it, curb the excesses of man. Thus, in traditional societies, it is not uncommon to find some people who still give expressions to their wicked, selfish, and brutal nature that threaten the harmony of the society and individual freedom. That is, in traditional societies, there existed deviant behaviors which deviate from the norms and values of the people, and which society frowns at. The traditional people had behaviors they could regard as “crime” in their primitive era (of which some of these “crime” in the traditional era have been co-opted into the criminal laws of the modern state); and as Hobbes suggested there must have been a “constituted body” (Appadoria, 2003:22) and for some crime control methods among the traditional people to help curb man's selfish and 'unreasonable' behaviors to maintain societal harmony. So what is crime?

In simple term, crime can be defined or referred to as, any wrongs against society (Okere, 1995). To be sure, all the modern states of the World were once traditional: right from the advanced nations to the modern states of Africa, were once traditional societies; and as such had some deviant behaviors regarded as “crime” within their indigenous cultural milieu. They may not have had formal criminal laws like the present day modern states, but there were behaviors they could regard as having broken the indigenous norms or that have gone extra juridical to what is acceptable by the natives.

For instance, the Native Americans (The American Indians) had deviant behaviors they could be regard as “crime” and methods of controlling them in their traditional era. Similarly, the traditional African societies, like the Ancient Kingdom of Ghana, like other

African countries, Kenya, Zambia, Tanzania, Zimbabwe etc. had behaviors in their traditional setting they could regard it as a “crime” even though they may not have had formal criminal codes then. Typically, in traditional Nigerian society, prior to the advent of the British Colonial Masters and their formal laws, acts like murder, adultery, witchcraft etc. were regarded as behaviors (“Criminal behaviors”) that were crossed the societal normative boundary, and attracted some traditional crime control measures so as to maintain societal harmony. Therefore, traditional methods of crime control connote the olden day methods or primitive crime control measures by which the native people controlled or punished behaviors that have broken their indigenous norms. Thus, in the light of the foregoing, and for the sake of stating the reason for this paper, we shall be focusing on discussion on the traditional methods of crime control in Bekwarra Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

The major objectives of the study is to critically examine the traditional methods of controlling criminal behavior in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria, so as to appreciate the effectiveness of the traditional methods in crime control.

Conceptual Clarifications:

There are certain few terms in the study that needs some clarification for the purpose of proper understanding, in view of this, we will like to clarify them. These include but not limited to; crime, crime control, traditional methods.

- **Crime:** it is an action or omission which constitutes an offence and is punishable by law. In other words, it refers to wrongs against society (Okere, 1995). An action can only be considered a crime if declared as such by the relevant applicable laws (Farmer, 2008). A crime is a public wrong which are forbidden and punishable by law (Martin, 2003) in present societies (Martian stakes), for any action to be considered as crime, there must be presence of the element of an action of doing something wrong” accompanied by the element of “the intent to do something wrong” (Martin 2003) However, it should be noted that, while every crime violates the law, not every violation of law is crime. Substantively, under public law crime is any wrongful actions against the state; while wrongful acts between individual are regarded as 'civil wrong' and are punishable under civil procedures within the private law (actions like breach of contract between individuals, etc.).
- **Crime Control:** This refers to methods or measures taken to reduce crime in society. Similarly, it connotes a form of social control which includes a broad range of methods used in society that aim to reduce or prevent the occurrence of criminal behaviour. Modern methods of controlling crime include those used by the state, such as policing strategies, courts the use of punishment etc. (Christie, 2017). Additionally, crime control is also an approach that focuses on protecting society from criminals by regulating criminal conduct and justice, the idea is that by punishing those who commit crime, the rest of the people will be deterred from committing crime

frequently.

➤ **Traditional method**

This implies an olden method of doing something or carrying out a task. Hence, traditional method of crime control would suggest the olden day's method or primitive method of crime control as opposed to modern methods.

Literature review:

The concept of crime – An overview: The concept of crime is quite complex in that is perceived differently from different angles, and is relative to time and spatial contexts. The functionalists (like Emile Durkheim) for instance perceive crime as acts which depart from the value consensus of the society, which strongly offend the 'collective conscience' (Haralambos and Horlborn, 2004) To him, criminal laws and the control agents like the police, the court etc. Are playing legitimate roles in society as they are translating shared values into action. On the contrary, those of the Maxxian tradition/conflict perspective (like, William Chambliss, Frank Pearce and John Young etc.) perceive crime and its social control agencies as reflecting and serving the ruling class interests (Haralambos & Horlborn, 2004). That is the political class will define any behaviour which does not serve their vested interest as crime. The concept of crime connotes the intentional commission of an act usually deemed social harmful or dangerous, and is specifically prohibited and punishable under criminal law. By criminal law, we refer to a body of law that define criminal offences & fixes punishment for convicted persons. That is an act can't be said to constitute a crime except it is contained in a state's criminal codes. For instance, in Nigeria, some acts considered as crime state's include, kidnaping, murder, human trafficking, child sexual abuse, corruption, domestic violence organized crime, smuggling, burglary, cybercrimes, money laundering etc. (Doris 2022). For the sake of clarifications, criminal offences may be grouped into three broad types (Okere, 1995) namely; the first group: acts of physical violence, (eg. Murder, rape, assault, etc.); second group: acts of infringements on properly rights (eg. Theft, burglary) and third group: a broad range of actions labelled as crime against health, morals and public safety (eg. Prostitution gambling, pornography, drug abuse, drunkenness and in some areas homosexual).

Thotakuru (2014) sees crime as, a public wrong. To him, is an act against what the state considers as criminal law. Although, each society may define what is constitute a crime differently; relative to time and space, the following elements must be present in any act considered as crime. This includes the individual, no crime cannot be can be committed without a person; for there to be an act of crime there must be an individual who has an intention and is prepared to commit crime.

The second is the “intent” there must be an element that is the stop 'guilty mind' for a crime to be committed “intention” to commit such a crime must be established. Third the 'action' element, that is a “guilty act”. For a crime to be committed, there must be “an action” (usually, physical, e.g. injury: mental or physical or monetary which violates the state's law) alongside with the “intent” to commit such act. Social factor like poor up bring, drug abuse, family disorganization, unemployment, poverty and many more may act as inducement for individual to commit crime.

The above may define what constitute a crime in a modern state. However, it is

important to note that modern states were sometimes or once traditional communities, or societies having their native norms and values that define what crime is to them, in traditional communities, all actions that disrupt communal harmony are considered as crime to them (Masitera 2019). For instance, in the traditional society of North America (the American Indian natives), what was regarded as anti-social behavior or crime among them was usually determined through a tribal consensus (USA Department of Justice, 1996). Among indigenous American, acts alcoholism, family violence, incest, sexual assault and homicide were considered as crime in their traditional era (Poupart, 2002). In the same vein, African societies in their traditional era have actions they considered as crime. The African legal culture fronts at any improper behaviour viewed as capable of being inimical to the legal norms and disrupting social equilibrium (Chinyere, 2022). In Ancient kingdom of Ghana, for instance, denial of debt or shedding of blood were considered as crime among the natives of the Ancient kingdom of Ghana in 9th & 8th century (ushistory.org.2022): and part of their justice system was to give the accused a concoction to drink at the trial at the king's court, if he/she vomited; he/she was declared innocent of the crime; but if he/she did not vomit at all, it means their he/she was found guilty of the offence or the crime (ushistory.org.2022). In the same manner, traditional Nigerian societies in their traditional era had actions they considered as crime like, witchcraft, incest, assault, adultery, evasion of duties, marital abuse, cruelty etc. (Chinyere 2022). And some of their traditional crime control methods include fine payment, banishment, death penalty, oath taking at shrines etc. Igbo tribe, for authorities, the caution or institutions that initiate such control methods include, the King (The Eze), Umunna, (Council of elders), Okpala (First sons of each extended family), the masquerades (Nmanwa) etc. Therefore, from the backdrop of this study, the common thing among all traditional societies (be it the traditional societies of the North American or traditional societies of Africa) as regards what constitutes the concept of crime in their traditional setting are actions which are against the society.

Udoh, Mboho & Effiong (2020) opined that, in a nut shell, security is the act of seeing the survival and peaceful existence of people in the society. As observed by Effiong, Udousung & Udoh (2018), societies generally across the world, especially in Africa, have had very disturbing phases in their history as characterized by unending inter-group rivalries. Udoh & Udousoro (2024) argued that, the problem is such that one hardly goes through the pages of a news paper without the disturbing stories of youths restiveness, violence, and crime in different places across the globe and within Nigeria. As seen by Udoh, and Udousoro (2024), in most cases, the advantages of tricycle include transport service, job creation, income generation and equity. But criminals also patronize them. To Mboho, Udoh & Udo(2014) the challenge has become one of the effective and efficient management of its wealth to the advantage of a larger fraction of its citizenry.

The General concept of traditional methods of crime control in Nigeria

Prior to Western Colonization, African traditional societies according to Uyang *et al* (2013) had various traditional means or channel through which the native people controlled crime and maintain social order. These include, but not limited to, the council of elders, chief, village heads etc. Whose functions is to interpret the norms of behavior in a particular community and adjudicate justice, as passed down from generation to generation. According to Hobbes (Onwe and Eze, 2019; Appadoria, 2003), man in the state of nature is wicked,

brutal and selfish) Therefore, the indigenous people in their state of nature (primitive society) traditional era must have part to place in certain crime prevent measures to curb the excess of those who may term to be wicked; brutal or selfish – whose actions or activities break the social harmony of the people or the society. Among the major Nigeria traditional ethnic groups like the Hausa/Fulani, for instance; their crime control mechanism revolved around their constitute political institution and agents of social control which included, the Waziri (heads of all the officials), the Galadima (in charge of the capital), the Madaki (the commanders of the army), the Dogari (head of the police), etc. (Dibie, 2018). In the same way, the Yoruba traditional society, had their Oyomesi (the kingmakers), the Oba and Baale (who had spiritual powers to check the excess of any autocratic Alafin), the Are-ona-kakanfo (head of army), the Ogboni society (who had judicial powers for preservation of their cultural values, and administer the 'Ocultic Calabash' as a crime control measure) etc. (Dibie, 2018). Similarly, the Ibo traditional society had their traditional crime 'control measures' discharged through their traditional institutions like the Eze's court, the council of elders, Okpala, Umuada, age grade, the masquerade, etc.

In the same vein, in Bekwarra, the traditional crime control methods in typical traditional Nigerian society according to Onwe and Eze (2013) include, fine payment, compensation, ritual cleansing, trial by ordeal, ridicule and gossips, the masquerade institution, banishment, ostracism and capital punishment etc.

Sequel to the above, we shall explain each of them as used:

1. Fines/Compensation: This involves the imposition of damage (in monetary value) on offenders to compensate the victim or as a ransomed to the entire society
2. Ritual cleansing: In Nigerian traditional society, violation of certain norms and values were regarded as “land discretion or defilement” as case may be (in Igbo parlance)” (Ime ruala). The remedial require ritual measure was a form of ritual cleansing: the offences that could require ritual cleansing include incest, adultery, murdered.
3. Trial by ordeals: This involves providing the innocence of the accused. It involved, oath taking, administration of concoction or invocation of juju, etc.
4. Ridicules & gossips: Deviation from certain societal values, and norms usually attracted some unfavorable or negative reactions/disapproval from one's significant others (family relative, friends or age mates). This could serve as both a punitive and preventive measures in controlling criminal or deviant behaviors. One, could as a result of what people would say, conform to the normative behavior of society.
5. The masquerade institution: The use of masquerades in traditional societies of Nigeria acted as a social control mechanism for control of criminal behaviors. The masquerade would appear in the night as a supernatural being and attack the offender.
6. Ostracism: This involved serving social contact with the offender that is deliberately isolating the offenders in every socio-economic activity like, market, farm and community gatherings etc. this has very high psychological or emotional implication on the offender. It can further lead to the offenders to kill himself/herself or suffer depression.
7. Banishment: In Nigerian societies, traditionally, this involved sending the offender

away from his or her community (what modern states could call exile) this might include cases of persistent stealing, murderer, witchcraft, case of poisoning another member of the community etc.

The above mentioned traditional crime control measures are typical of Nigerian traditional societies. Although, the crime controls of some of the various ethnic groups in Nigeria may vary in some aspects or be similar due to cultural differences for example, in some of them, the structural institutions through which traditional crime control measures are being discharged are centralized (like among the Hausa and Yoruba crime control/justice system); while in other ethnic groups like among Igbos the structural institutions through which the crime control measures are being discharged are rather decentralized or fragmented.

In spite of their peculiarities, one important thing among them is the religious aspect in the structural discharge of the crime control measures. Religion played a very vital influence in the crime control mechanism. According to (Okere, 1995:165), religion aspect of power is institutionalized in their traditional crime control method. The religious aspect is so institutionalized like it becomes very difficult to distinguish these customs from religion. Okere (1995:165) argued that “traditional religious head or priest is almost always associated with interpretation and enforcement of rules of social behaviour”.

Traditional Methods of Crime Control in Bekwarra Local Government Area of Cross River State:

Bekwarra community is chosen as a study area because of its traditional nature of its crime control measure that is still in vogue and co-exists with the modern crime control systems. This can be achieved by giving a brief history of Bekwarra people:

Brief History of Bekwarra Nation:

The history of the Bekwarra ethnic nationality can be traced to over 400 years ago to the family of Ogar Agba. Obudu Agba, Igede Agba, Ubube Agba and Bekwarra Agba were the families that made up of Bekwarra. The history had it that, they lived with each other in harmony and peace, not until a new baby was born into the family. There was a lowery called “Une-ushi” in where every newborn in the family must wear to signify the family cultural heritage and as a way to welcome a new born baby to the family (Omangu, 2012). The controversy which created a problem among the members of the family was the issue that the new born has over worn their family symbolic artifact for too long, as such members of the Agba's family demanded that the so-called “Une-ushi” be removed. The controversy continued to manifest until the baby was eventually killed. This incident resulted to the separation of the historic Agba's family. The unfortunate circumstances which emanated as of then, marked the very beginning of the Bekwarra nation (Omagu, 2006).

Bekwarra Agba comprises of Odama and Ashide who were sons of the Ogar Agba. The history had it that they migrated away from Obudu where they all resided before the crisis to Utugwang village. Odama and Ashide with their family became uncomfortable with the unreceptive nature of Utugwang people. The most notable was when the host community (Utugwang) refused to give the visitors drinking water, when they requested for, they were denied of their request. This incident made Odama to say in Obudu native language

“Bekworor” being interpreted as “let us go”. Therefore, the name Bekwarra was gotten from the phrase Bekworor and that was how they left to find themselves in the land called Bekwarra today.

The geographical area which is today called Bekwarra, when Odama and Ashide's family and some areas had already been occupied by some few families. Among them were the Agidi's family (Aladum) which are now called Ibiaragidi community. But however, no meaningful emphasis is given to these families that were existing before the arrival of the children of Bekwarra Agba in the land because there was unifying factor amongst them.

The beginning of the Bekwarra nation, was marked by the arrival of Odama and Ashide. Their children scattered all through the length and breadth of the geographical boundary of the small nation. They have the same language, cultures, traditions and values. All this explains why they remain many similarities between the people of Obudu, Mbube, Igede and Bekwarra in terms of tradition and language up till today (Omagu, 2006).

In the pre-colonial era, Bekwarra, traditional leaders played an important role through their offices in the usual administration of their territory and the lives of the folks. Functions were exercised sometimes by elders or councilors or communal groups of judicial institutions. Among Bekwarra people for instance, the mechanisms of social control and legal system is bestowed on traditional leaders, congress of chiefs, age grades, chiefs, ancestral cults, religious bodies, local deities and many others. These institutions usually employed different mechanism which were all geared towards peaceful co-existence of members. As in many African towns, the representations of the chief's council (Ike Udiara) in Bekwarra are the heads of various families (Omagu and Amaechi, 2014). Belief in Atabouchi (Supreme God) as the purveyor of human existence, working through such intermediaries as ancestral spirits and the elders as the lynch pin, motivated all to obedience.

Before discussing the crime control methods of traditional Bekwarra people it is important to know what constitute or what traditional peoples regard as crime among them. It is pertinent to note that among the traditional people of Bekwarra nation, there are several levels of offences exist that the people considered or regarded as crime.

These includes but not limited to the following:

1. Aji (stealing)
2. Igbang (fornication)
3. Ipiri (adultery)
4. Uchia (enam k' Ukwo) witchcraft
5. Ichibibi (eha k' iriji) wizard

Traditional crime control methods among the Bekwarra people

In Bekwarra community or nation, anyone who commits the aforementioned crimes or offences are usually sanctioned with following crime control methods. The essence as it is in every society is to use these measures as social control mechanism, both as a punitive as well as a preventive measure.

1. Atabouchi (Supernatural & spirit) or land cleansing; The traditional people of Bekwarra view their relationship with the spirit world as a scared bond. They regard any serious offence like “Ipiri” (adultery) as offence committed against 'Atabouchi' (God) and humanity, such a crime, to them, has weakened their relationship between

the native people and “Atabouchi” (God): The offender is mandated to provide essential items like dog, fowl, tortoise, plus pieces of kolanut, palm wine etc. And depends on the gravity of the offence. The purpose of it is to use these items to appeal or cleanse the polluted land and restore the relationship of Bekwarra people with the spirit (Atabouchi). No matter how costly the prescribed ritual items might be, the offender as a punishment for his or her acts must provide the items. If he or she is incapable of affording the prescribed ritual items, he/her kinsmen or extended family must rally round him to support him to provide the prescribed ritual items for the land cleansing.

2. Uchia (Enam k' Ukwo) witchcraft: This is ostracism/ex communication (Efuo wo Uchu) this is an extreme degree of crime control method among Bekwarra people. Bekwarra people call it 'Efuo wo Ucha' after he/she has been tried (Efuo wo uchuon) and found guilty. When one is ostracized from the community, he/her relationship with others fellows is completely cut off. Everyone will boycott the offender in all manner of socio-economic affairs, including isolating him/her at market, at stream, at farm; it may even affect his nuclear family also where no one would have contact with his/her family because of him.
3. Ichibibi (eha k' Iriji) wizard: This banishment, banishment is as grievous as death penalty. It is what the modern state call. 'exile'. It means a process by which an offender is expelled from his/her clan temporarily or permanently. Only offenders who commit the crimes considered as defiling the land get banished. To Bekwarra man, the land is polluted, the earth goodness (Atabouchi) get angry so the offender must be whisked off from the community immediately before the anger of the gods spread to the nearest community. For instance, sometime in 2023, a certain man from one of the village in Bekwarra who was accused of killing his brother in the village. While the police were still making their procedural investigation and arrest, the youngman and his entire family were banished from the community permanently. Their houses and properties were burnt down by the angry youths and the elders of the community. This can be likened to Chinua Achebe in his book tittle “Things fall Apart” the case of Okonkwo, when he unintentionally killed a clansman – “the only course open to Okonkwo was to flee from the village”. It was a grievous offence against goodness (Atabouchi), the man who committed this crime must flee from the community (Okere, 1995:182). In fact, banishment is worse than death penalty, especially where it entails banishment for life; the banished person will no longer return to his/her community in life time; and at the event of he/her death, he/she is buried outside the homeland.
4. Uchon (Oath taking) This is main crime control method among the traditional people of Bekwarra. Usually a designated person is chosen to conduct the Oath taking. The setting can be at village square, but normally a certain man in his shrine will conduct the Oath taking. It is better for the accused to say the truth before the time than to take the Oath; because if he/she is guilty a certain leave on a scared stone, will gum he/her bottom and he/she two eyes redished, proved that he/she is guilty of the crime. But if

the accused is free from the accusation, he/she proved innocent, and so cleared.

This list of traditional crime control among the traditional Bekwarra people community in Cross River State, Nigeria may not be exhaustive, but the above methods reflect the traditional crime control methods practice among the Bekwarra people.

Theoretical framework: Anomie theory:

The major proponents of this theory are: Emile Durkheim, Herbert Spencer, Talcoth Parsons and Robert Merton. According to Emile Durkheim, in primitive societies, there existed mechanical solidarity in which cultural folk's laws, and cultural mores and values controlled and guide people's behavior. But as society becomes bigger and larger, more expansive and become complex, there would be shift from mechanical solidarity to more complex organic solidarity, in which Chinua Achebe said or called "a center cannot longer holds" resulting to increase in division of labour and society become heterogeneous or heterogeneity. The result would be that the traditional forms of social control that hold the society together have been rendered ineffective. Subsequent upon this anomie and normlessness become the order of the day and replaced the former state of solidarity. Under these condition individuals strive to reach their goals the society set for them by all means readiness and most effective means available to them regardless of the moral prohibitions of society, hence the high rate of crime or deviant behavior. This theory, clearly explain why crime rate has increased in recent times. Other security agencies, like police instead of carrying out their constitutional roles have resorted to sharp practices without their defined roles or duties, such as receiving fortifications, extra judicial killings of being part of hatching and fronting kidnaping, armed robberies and associated or criminalities.

The justification for adopting it as the theoretical framework is because its thesis is more relevant in discussing the control methods of crime which this discourse focuses on. Thus from the inference of Anomie theory; one may conclude that the traditional methods of crime control in traditional societies will help restrain people from community crime.

Methodology

The study adopts qualitative approach and focuses on descriptive that enable the researchers to gain insight into the methods of traditional crime control in Bekwarra Local Government Area. The primary sources of data are one-on-one interview, Focus Group Discussion (FGDs), and key informant interview (KI) with community elders, the chief, the victim of the crime, the security agencies like police. Sources of data: Desk review of the extant literature, examining the methods and the effective used of traditional methods of crime controls extant literature, relevant documents, newspaper, magazine, article seminar papers were all content analysed.

Findings

The findings showed that crime control measures used or adopted by Bekwarra serves as deferent to prevent people from community crime or would be culprit.

- ❖ Traditional methods of crime control measures may be primitive in nature, but they are very effective in preventing criminal behaviors among the traditional communities.

- ❖ It was also discovered that traditional methods of crime control before the advent of the Colonial Masters was more effective because the community or communities were guided by the norms values and customs of the society (community solidarity)
- ❖ Society itself may also be contributory factors in crime rate

Conclusion

Having made some relevant finding from the investigations the paper therefore concludes that crime is inevitable in all human societies both (modern or traditional) crime control methods are essential and most remedy to combat crime to achieve societal harmony, extreme social order can be maintained and sustained

Recommendations

- In the traditional set up, the orthodox methods of fighting crime should be adequately complemented with modern methods of control with the help of established regulatory and enforcement agencies
- Traditional societies and their institutions should be encouraged by government to retain some of their traditional crime control methods as some of these measures have proved to be effective in controlling crime at the community levels (the grassroots level of the government). There should be synergy between the traditional and modern crime control methods to effectively curb crime to the grassroots.
- The traditional crime control methods, can review and adjust some of their crime control measures that infringe on individual's human rights

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